

On the relationship between gender inequalities and regional dissemination patterns in Latin America

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Abstract

Throughout the 20th century, an academic circuit established itself in Latin America, focusing on research topics specifically relevant to the region. However, its activity is highly vulnerable to the region's pervasive political and economic instability and, despite having a relatively gender-balanced research community, women remain underrepresented in scientific publishing. Through an analysis of scientific publications indexed in Dimensions, this article explores the relationship between gender inequalities in the scientific field and the integration of Latin American researchers into the regional and global academic circuits between 1993 and 2022. Our findings show cycles of strengthening and weakening of the regional circuit. Despite a general increase in women's participation in research over the period, gender disparities persist: women tend to be more involved in the regional circuit, while men hold a stronger presence in the global circuit.

1. Introduction

Latin American countries have a similar number of men and women scientists. According to UNESCO (2019), women account for 45.1% of the scientific workforce, a considerably higher proportion than the corresponding figure at the global level (29.3%). However, women are still underrepresented in scientific publishing (Albornoz et al., 2018; Beigel et al., 2023) and face greater difficulties in getting promoted within the scientific system, even when they exhibit levels of productivity similar to men's (Gallardo, 2022; Jonkers, 2011; López-Bassols et al., 2018). It is widely acknowledged that this situation is detrimental to the development of scientific knowledge since gender-diverse groups are more likely to make novel scientific contributions (Hofstra et al., 2020) and diversity in the scientific workforce drives the expansion of the knowledge base (Kozlowski et al., 2022). Although Latin America shows great potential for achieving equal gender participation in science, the specific issues the region¹ faces still

¹ Throughout the article, we will use the term region to denote Latin America and the Caribbean, as per the United Nations Regional Groups classification.

hinder the fulfillment of this goal. The factors that shape this phenomenon are diverse, ranging from the social roles attributed to men and women—which influence both labor division and topic selection (Bello, 2020; Ceci & Williams, 2011; Shen, 2013)—to issues related to the hostility of the work environment (Fox, 1991; Spoon et al., 2023), collaboration (Ductor et al., 2023; Holman & Morandin, 2019) and authorship disagreements (Ni et al., 2021). However, higher percentages of women in the academic workforce may not necessarily stem from positive factors: parity may be found in countries where scientific work is not associated with high degrees of social and economic capital, or even signal brain drain² (Sugimoto & Larivière, 2023).

A range of countries with varying levels of research and development investments, science and technology infrastructure, and human capital can be found in Latin America, where scientific activity is primarily funded by the public sector and is therefore highly vulnerable to the region's pervasive political and economic instability (Ciocca & Delgado, 2017; Rojas Cifuentes et al., 2023; Salager-Meyer, 2008). Countries in this region can be considered semi-peripheral, as they are not as resource-constrained as the peripheries, but still have access to considerably fewer resources and face more economic and institutional hurdles (often due to political instability) than the centers (Beigel et al., 2023; Bennett, 2014; Céspedes, 2021). In this regard, when allocating resources, science and technology policies in the region tend to favour the natural or technical sciences over the social sciences and humanities, as their findings, which can be applied to industry, are viewed as a productive means for achieving greater economic development (Paz Enrique et al., 2022).

A strong regional academic circuit thrives alongside the global academic circuit in Latin America, addressing region-specific concerns through articles that are often in Spanish and Portuguese rather than in English (Beigel, 2014; Céspedes, 2021). This academic circuit was first established in the 1950s along with the emergence of Latin American intergovernmental institutions such as ECLAC³, FLACSO⁴, and later CLACSO⁵. Its importance decreased during the 1970s and 1980s with the rise of military dictatorships, and encountered further challenges in the 1990s after democracy was restored as neoliberal policies brought severe cutbacks for higher education and science. This circuit regained a central role at the turn of this Century with the adoption of post-neoliberal policies that once more prioritized the funding of science and higher education (Beigel, 2014), and supported the development of regional systems of scientific publications such as SciELO, Latindex, and Redalyc (Beigel, 2013). Since the 2010, however, the resurgence of neoliberal-oriented governments has led to challenges resembling those of earlier decades⁶, and in some cases to the dismantling of national scientific systems (De Ambrosio & Koop, 2024).

The existence of a regional academic circuit is strongly associated with the development of research projects that focus on issues relevant to the region, with the production of articles in a language that the general population can understand, thus ensuring greater diffusion and impact within national boundaries). However, the symbolic capital accumulated at the international level circuit is more easily transferable to the regional circuit than the opposite. Thus, scientists

² The author's analysis suggests that in cases of brain drain, women are likely to be the ones left behind (Sugimoto & Larivière, 2023, p. 36).

³ Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean.

⁴ Spanish acronym for the Latin American Faculty of Social Sciences.

⁵ Spanish acronym for Latin American Council of Social Sciences.

⁶ Specifically, in 2016, for the first time since the year 2000, there was a decrease in the resources dedicated to R&D (RICYEL, 2023).

who are successful in the global academic circuit face fewer obstacles in their careers than those who remain primarily involved in regional circuits (Beigel, 2014). In this regard, it is worth noting that evaluation systems favouring publication in international journals⁷ lead to the unintended consequence of directing researchers' attention toward topics relevant to central⁸ countries (van Bellen & Larivière, 2024; Vessuri et al., 2014, p. 650).

Economic crises and uncertainty have led to funding shortages in Latin America, with negative effects on scientific productivity—mainly resulting from inadequate budgets and salaries, substandard levels of infrastructure and equipment, and the high cost and limited supply of reagents—(Ciocca & Delgado, 2017; Salager-Meyer, 2008). Previous research has shown the effects of gender stereotypes, unequal distribution of care work and parenting on women's careers (Bello, 2020; Carpes et al., 2022), as well as the presence of strong gender biases in the allocation of science and technology public grants (Fiorentin et al., 2023). Furthermore, Beigel et al. (2023) found that, in Argentina and Brazil, productivity gaps between men and women widen when considering the language of their publications. This study aims to advance this line of research through a comparative analysis of the integration of women and men affiliated with Latin American institutions into global and regional academic circuits. Moreover, it aims to expand upon this analysis by considering the effects of economic and political instability on the development of the regional scientific system.

2. Methods

This article is based on the Dimensions database (Herzog et al., 2020). We examine the publications of Latin America-affiliated authors⁹ between 1993 and 2022. Our data consist of 1,845,772 articles and conference proceedings and 3,779,387 distinct authors. The metadata includes authors' given and family names, which are used to infer gender. The gender disambiguation algorithm builds on the method presented in Larivière et al. (2013), which uses census data and country-specific lists of men and women names to assign probable gender to given names.¹⁰ Applying this algorithm, it was possible to infer the gender of 70.7% of the authors in the dataset; therefore, our analysis is limited to this subset of the population. Gender is considered in a binary way, as other genders can only be assigned through self-identification. This is an acknowledged limitation of the study.

Drawing on the criteria applied by van Bellen & Larivière (2024), we operationalize insertion in the regional academic circuit through publication in a journal located in Latin America (for articles) or publication at a conference held in Latin America (for conference proceedings). Journal's location information is retrieved from Ulrich's Periodicals Directory using the ISSN, which identifies journals present in the Dimensions database; on the other hand, information on the location of conferences is retrieved from the database's metadata. Given the constraints of the available data, the following countries were considered (ordered by the number of

⁷ Latin American journals included in ISI (Institute for Scientific Information) usually have a low impact factor (Paz Enrique et al., 2022), and are therefore considered less prestigious than those published in central countries.

⁸ In this context, we expand on Alatas' (2003) conceptualization to define central countries to be those that command considerable recognition and prestige and can therefore determine research agendas, problems areas, methods of research, and standards of excellence. Additionally, scientists in these countries tend to consider the disclosure of the location of their studies to be largely irrelevant due to the universal significance they attribute to their findings (Baber, 2003; Castro Torres & Albrez-Gutierrez, 2022).

⁹ Only the first institutional affiliation of each author is considered.

¹⁰ In the case of certain countries such as Russia, family names are also necessary to infer gender (note that Latin American author's collaborators come from all over the world).

publications in the database): Brazil, Mexico, Argentina, Chile, Colombia, Peru, Venezuela, Uruguay, Bolivia, and Paraguay.

Finally, applying the model by Grootendorst (2022), we used articles' abstract and title to train a multilingual¹¹ semi-supervised¹² BERTopic model to infer the topic of scientific publications defining 100 publications as the minimum topic size, which created a model with 532 topics. KeyBERTInspired was used to improve topic representation, which was later refined by hand-labeling topics to improve their readability.

3. Results

The evolution of women's participation in scientific production in Latin America shows a constant increase throughout the period, both in terms of the proportion of women authors and of women authorship. However, we find a persistent gap between the proportion of women authors and the share of articles authored by women (Figure 1A). Our results also show that the proportion of scientific publications in Latin American journals or conferences grew and subsequently diminished (Figure 1B).

Using these trends, we divided our analysis into three decades: 1993-2002 (a decade marked by the gradual strengthening of the regional academic circuit), 2003-2012 (the strongest phase of the regional circuit), and 2013-2022 (a period of gradual weakening of the regional circuit). It is worth noting that the gap between the proportion of women authors and publications authored by women narrows until 2012 and then expands during the next decade. The sharp increase in the proportion of articles authored by women during the strongest phase of the regional circuit can be attributed to the fact that women have an authorship rate that is 19%¹³ higher within this circuit than in the global academic circuit.

These fluctuating trends reflect the impact of economic and political instability on Latin American scientific systems. During periods of economic abundance and higher public expenditure—such as the decade ranging from 2003 to 2012—(Moreno-Brid & Garry, 2016; Rojas Cifuentes et al., 2023) the regional scientific community strengthens, opening up new opportunities for participation, particularly for women.

¹¹ A multilingual model was employed because articles in the corpus were written in English, Portuguese, and Spanish (along with a small proportion in other languages). In this regard, stopwords in these three languages were removed, as well as words belonging to snippets of LaTeX code that could be found in the data.

¹² Using discipline labels provided by Dimensions.

¹³ This calculation is not presented on a yearly basis due to limited data availability in the initial years of the period, resulting in excessive variability.

Figure 1: Evolution of the proportion of women authors and women authorship (fractional count) (A) and the proportion of articles and conference proceedings published in Latin American journals or conferences (B). Dotted lines mark years 2003 and 2012.

Participation in global or regional research activities is a function of the characteristics of the disciplines in which researchers are active. For instance, social sciences and humanities have deeper roots in their local context (Vessuri et al., 2014), and therefore national journals play an important role in its dissemination. Given women's higher representation in these disciplines (Sugimoto & Larivière, 2023), it's reasonable to expect them to show a greater involvement in the regional academic circuit. Figure 2 shows that women systematically publish more than expected within the regional academic circuit, even when controlling for disciplines and specialties in which they are active. Furthermore, this trend has strengthened over time, women are increasingly underrepresented in the international academic circuit with respect to their male peers in Latin America. This finding is particularly compelling when considering there was a decline in the relative volume of scientific publications within this circuit throughout the period; despite the global trend in the Latin American scientific community to reorient its research towards the global academic circuit, women exhibited the opposite behavior.

Figure 2: Ratio between real and expected proportion of articles and conference proceedings published in Latin American journals or conferences for men and women given the disciplinary distribution for each group¹⁴.

To better understand how topic choice relates with women’s and men’s participation in the global and regional academic circuits, we compiled the main topics of their publications and of publications in the regional and global circuits within disciplines of the social sciences and medical and health sciences. These two areas were selected because of their size, high percentage of women authors, and their focus on both local and global issues. The correspondence between topics and disciplines is based on the discipline to which the majority of articles is associated. In cases where no single discipline dominates, the topic is considered multidisciplinary.

Tables 1 and 2 suggest that women focus mainly on topics related to children, adolescents, and elderly people’s care and rights (such as *Children's Rights*, *Elderly Care*, *Newborn pain*, *Kangaroo Care*, and *Adolescent Sexuality*) while considering issues specifically relevant to the region such as the role of schools in children’s nutrition or the high prevalence of eating disorders (Kolar et al., 2016). Moreover, they address issues particularly relevant to low-income countries such as *Infection Prevention in Hospitals* or *Food Security*. On the other hand, Latin American men authors mainly specialize in topics that are not specifically related to the region’s needs; a noteworthy example is Cancer, whose research is largely concentrated in the Global North (Miao et al., 2022), where cancer mortality is higher (Bray et al., 2018). It is also worth noting that we observe locally relevant topics whose research is led by men (such as Deforestation), but these issues are not specific to the region; instead, they constitute challenges of global importance.

¹⁴ Results are aggregated by decade due to insufficient data availability in the first decade to conduct a year-by-year analysis.

Table 1: Main topics addressed by research led by men and women for social sciences.

Social Sciences			
Top 10		Bottom 10	
Topic	Women authorship (%)	Topic	Women authorship (%)
Children's Rights	76.6%	Fuzzy Logic	17.0%
Nutrition in Schools	75.0%	Lean Practices in Organizations	22.8%
Autism	67.4%	Soccer	23.9%
Euthanasia	66.7%	Dairy production	24.0%
Caregivers' Resilience	65.6%	Government Projects	29.7%
Eating disorders	63.9%	Family Enterprises	32.7%
Elderly Care	59.8%	Deforestation	35.2%
Environmental Education	58.9%	Internet Usage	36.1%
Psychotherapy	57.6%	Audiovisual Education	38.4%
Food Security	57.4%	Coffee	38.9%

Table 2: Main topics addressed by research led by men and women for medical and health sciences.

Medical And Health Sciences			
Top 10		Bottom 10	
Topic	Women authorship (%)	Topic	Women authorship (%)
Ulcers	74.8%	Cancer	14.1%
Newborn pain	74.6%	Subdural Hematoma	18.6%
Cerebral Paralysis	73.8%	Genomic Prediction	19.0%
Turner Syndrome	71.2%	Carpal Tunnel	21.1%
Puberty	70.2%	Brain Connectivity Analysis	22.8%
Violence Against Women	69.5%	Frog Muscles	24.4%
Kangaroo Care	66.9%	Cats' Spinal Cord	25.5%
Infection Prevention in Hospitals	66.8%	Cardiovascular Disease Risk Factors	25.8%
Adolescent Sexuality	66.1%	Pulmonary Hypertension	26.5%
Tinnitus	65.4%	Hydrocephalus	27.1%

The evidence presented in Table 4 shows that the main topics discussed within the regional circuit in the medical and health sciences address issues specifically relevant to the region such as *Recyclable Waste Pickers' health*, *Transgender Health* or the treatment of *Burnout*.¹⁵ On the other hand, as shown in Table 3, in the regional circuit the social sciences address topics of obvious relevance to the region such as the *Brazilian Healthcare System*, as well as cultural topics like *Photography*, *Cinema*, and *Theater*. Furthermore, we find topics primarily associated with caregiving in both disciplines which, as previously discussed, are predominantly studied by women researchers.

Table 3: Main topics addressed by scientific publications in the regional and global circuits for social sciences.

Social Sciences			
Top 10		Bottom 10	
Topic	Published in LA (%)	Topic	Published in LA (%)
Photography	89.6%	Bipolarity	10.5%
Brazilian Healthcare System	88.8%	Circular Business	14.6%
Cinema	84.3%	Gamification	15.2%
Theater	83.7%	Fuzzy Logic	21.1%
Environmental Education	83.5%	Musical Abilities	23.2%
Euthanasia	82.8%	Lean Practices in Organizations	24.2%
Children's Rights	82.4%	Family Enterprises	25.6%
Nutrition in Schools	75.5%	Musical Education	30.9%
Dairy production	73.1%	Government Projects	31.8%
Audiovisual Education	70.5%	Elderly Care	31.9%

¹⁵ Latin American workers' long hours contribute to a high burnout incidence (Marinakos, 2022).

Table 4: Main topics addressed by scientific publications in the regional and global circuits for medical and health sciences.

Medical And Health Sciences			
Top 10		Bottom 10	
Topic	Published in LA (%)	Topic	Published in LA (%)
Vaginal Prolapse	90.4%	Thermoreceptors	0.0%
Transgender Health	83.9%	Frog Muscles	0.0%
Violence Against Women	77.4%	Cocaine Neuroadaptation	1.4%
Cattle Disease	76.7%	Heme oxygenase	1.5%
Recyclable Waste Pickers	74.6%	Arthritis	2.9%
Epidemiology	74.4%	Cancer Cachexia	3.4%
Burnout	70.5%	Bisphenol Effects	3.5%
Kangaroo Care	70.5%	Mast Cells	3.9%
Broiler Nutrition	68.8%	Yeast Species	4.0%
Adolescent Sexuality	68.7%	Antidepressants	4.2%

In summary, our findings suggest that the existence of a regional knowledge dissemination circuit in Latin American is essential for the dissemination of women's research, as well as of research that addresses issues specifically relevant to the region. In this regard, it is not a lack of quality that leads certain scientists to disseminate their findings through local journals or conferences, but rather their focus on topics that may be of lesser importance to central countries.

4. Discussion

To understand the mechanisms underlying gender inequalities in Latin American science, it's essential to consider the region's unique characteristics. Our findings show a consistent increase in women's involvement in science over the 30 years analyzed in this paper, as well as a higher participation of women in the academic regional circuit compared to men—regardless of their distribution across disciplines and subdisciplines. However, our results also suggest that, although the region would greatly benefit from the strengthening of its regional academic circuit, which is used by researchers to disseminate findings specifically relevant to the region, political and economic instability hinder its development. In this regard, we identify three distinct phases between 1993 and 2022: an initial expansion of the regional academic circuit, followed by a phase where it remains strong, and finally its weakening. These findings closely align with the historical trajectory of the Latin American scientific system as portrayed in existing literature (Beigel, 2013, 2014).

As Beigel (2014) explains, scientists who manage a successful insertion into the global academic circuit will face fewer obstacles in their careers than those who remain mainly involved in regional circuits. However, as stated by Vessuri (2014), evaluation systems favouring publication in international journals lead to the unintended consequence of orienting researchers' focus towards topics relevant to central countries. Our findings therefore suggest that a fundamental factor structuring gender inequality in science within this region is the greater involvement of women in the regional academic circuit, focusing on the region's specific needs. In this regard, the picture we are presented with is analogous to the one generally observed in the labor market: not only do women face more obstacles in gaining access to the scientific field, but they also become part of a fundamentally precarious circuit where they address topics that, while crucial for Latin American communities, often receive less recognition, both nationally and internationally.

In this context, the lower relative participation of women in science in Latin America not only undermines the region's scientific production due to the increased propensity of gender-diverse groups to produce innovative outcomes (Hofstra et al., 2020), but also in terms of women's propensity to tackle issues of national relevance. In this regard, we argue that the Latin American scientific system faces two major challenges: first, fostering greater gender diversity in teams addressing issues of international relevance; and second, strengthening the regional academic circuit to ensure stable working conditions and equitable recognition for researchers addressing locally relevant topics.

Open science practices

This project relies on the *Dimensions* database as its main source, which is not openly available. We decided to use this database because we considered it to be the best source of information on publications authored by Latin-American researchers, both in terms of its quality and its coverage. The scripts used for this study are publicly available under: https://github.com/caropradier/latam_circuits.

Author contributions

Conceptualization: CP, DK, NS, TMW, VL

Methodology: CP, DK, TMW, VL

Software: CP, DK

Formal Analysis: CP, DK

Resources: VL

Data Curation: CP

Writing – Original Draft: CP

Writing – Review & Editing: CP, DK, NS, MN, TMW, VL

Visualization: CP

Supervision: VL

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Competing interests

The authors have no competing interests.

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